

THE INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL MARKETING AND PRODUCT QUALITY ON TIMES FLORIST PURCHASE DECISIONS IN PALU CITY

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of Digital Marketing and Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions at Times Florist in Palu City. The study used a quantitative method with data collection techniques through questionnaires distributed to 90 respondents using purposive sampling. Data were processed and analyzed using the SPSS.26 application through validity tests, reliability tests, classical assumption tests, multiple linear regression, F tests, t tests, and coefficients of determination. The results showed that Digital Marketing had a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. Product Quality also had a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. Simultaneously, both variables had a significant effect and were able to explain 85.1% of the variation in purchasing decisions. These findings confirm that optimizing digital marketing strategies and improving product quality are very important to improve consumer purchasing decisions.

Keywords: *Digital Marketing , Product Quality, Purchasing Decisions.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technology has transformed people's consumption patterns, particularly in how they search for information and interact with products. Increasingly easy internet access has encouraged people to shift to more practical activities, including online shopping and product selection (Agus & Armida, 2024) . This change has also given rise to a new type of consumer who is more critical, selective, and reliant on digital information before making purchasing decisions. In the marketing context, digital marketing has become an increasingly dominant strategy because it can reach consumers more quickly, broadly, and efficiently. Social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, and TikTok have become primary tools for businesses to showcase products, build engagement, and influence consumer purchasing interest through engaging visual content (Fista Natasya & Kuswibowo, 2023) . According to Rosalia (2025), Digital marketing is not just a trend, but has become an important element in modern business competition. This phenomenon is also evident in Palu City, where local businesses are increasingly utilizing social media to promote their products, particularly in the culinary, fashion, and creative sectors like bouquets. Consumers, particularly students and teenagers, are increasingly consulting catalogs and product information on social media before purchasing. This makes digital marketing a crucial strategy for increasing visibility and attracting potential customers.

Times Florist is a bouquet shop in Palu City that utilizes digital marketing as its primary promotional tool. The shop offers a variety of bouquets, including flower bouquets, snacks, money, skincare, and dolls. Promotions are conducted through Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp, featuring aesthetically pleasing product photos and videos. This digital marketing allows consumers to see the bouquets in person before purchasing, thus influencing their decision-making process. In addition to marketing aspects, product quality is also an important factor that influences purchasing decisions. Product quality includes the durability of materials, neatness of design, and suitability of results to consumer demand (Ratnasari & Ali, (2025) . Based on the researcher's observations, in running its business, Times Florist strives to maintain the quality of each product offered, both in terms of materials, durability, and neatness of design. However, this shop faces stiff competition because there are several other shops around the location that offer products with similar designs. This makes consumers often compare the quality, appearance, and durability of bouquets before deciding to buy. With increasingly tight competition around the campus area, maintaining and improving product quality is very important for Times Florist. Products with attractive designs, durable materials, and neat workmanship will be an added value in the eyes of consumers and can be a differentiator compared to other bouquet shops. Therefore, product quality at Times Florist plays a big role in influencing customer

satisfaction and purchasing decisions. Several previous studies have also shown that digital marketing and product quality have an influence on purchasing decisions (Sesandi et al., 2024 ; Soemadi, 2023 ; Fanlikhin et al., 2023). However, other studies have shown that digital marketing does not always have a significant effect (Rika Hubbina et al., 2023). Meanwhile, research by Bahri et al., (2023) again confirmed that both variables have a significant effect. This difference in results indicates an interesting research gap to study, especially in the context of local businesses such as Times Florist in Palu City. Based on the description above, the author is interested in conducting research entitled "The Influence of Digital Marketing and Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions at Times Florist, Palu City."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Marketing

Digital marketing utilizes various technology-based platforms such as the internet, mobile devices, mobile networks, and social media to directly reach consumers, both individually and within communities, including businesses. Through these platforms, marketers can convey information, build interactions, influence consumers, encourage product or brand purchases, and create profitable transactions and long-term relationships with consumers (Kotler et al., 2023:266) . Fadhli & Pratiwi, (2021) argue that digital marketing is an effort by a business or company to introduce products or services to the public or potential consumers via the internet, which usually conveys information in the form of interesting videos or photos using social media, websites, YouTube, e-commerce.

Kim (in Oktaviani et al., 2022) stated that there are four dimensions of digital marketing that have a strategic role in supporting promotional activities and interactions with consumers, namely:

- Interactive, is a promotional technique that allows for direct two-way communication between sellers and consumers, thereby increasing involvement and relationships.
- Incentive program, a promotional program that provides attractive offers, such as discounts or prizes, to attract consumers' interest in making purchases.
- Site design, an attractive and easy-to-use digital media display, thus giving a positive impression and making it easier for consumers to obtain information.
- Cost, Efficient pricing and comparable to product quality, so that it can influence purchasing decisions

Digital marketing is the achievement of goals through the use of digital media, data, and technology to convey information and interact with consumers. Digital marketing supports these goals in several ways, including (Chaffey & Chadwick, 2022:11):

- Identifying , namely digital interactions that become a source of information to understand consumer needs.
- Anticipating , which is utilizing online insights to adjust communications and promotions according to trends and audience needs.
- Satisfying , namely the effort to provide consumer satisfaction through a shopping experience that is more practical, fast, and according to expectations.

The relationship between digital marketing and purchasing decisions lies in its ability to influence consumer interest and confidence in a product. Through digital marketing strategies, sellers can convey information quickly, engagingly, and precisely, making it easier for consumers to learn about a product. Presenting engaging visual content and relevant promotions encourages consumers to make purchasing decisions.

Product Quality

According to Kotler & Keller, (2016: 156–158) product quality is anything that can be offered to the market to satisfy a desire or need, including physical goods, services, experiences, events, people, places, property, organizations, information, and ideas. Sari, (2021) stated that product quality is an action taken by a company to win competition in the market by establishing a set of meaningful differences in the products or services offered to differentiate the company's products from competitors' products, so that consumers can see or perceive that the quality product has the added value expected by consumers.

According to Handayani, (2022) there are five dimensions of product quality which consist of:

- Product features, product advantages such as design variations, choice of materials, or creative concepts that differentiate it from similar products.
- Product durability, the ability of a product assembly or arrangement to remain neat and presentable for a certain period of time.
- Product reliability, consistency of product results according to demand and can maintain its shape and appearance well.

- Conformity to specifications, Accuracy of the final product results with the previously agreed design, size and concept.
- Product aesthetics, Harmonious color, shape and composition to attract attention and be visually satisfying.

The relationship between product quality and purchasing decisions is evident in the extent to which a product meets consumer expectations and needs. A product with good quality, including aspects of durability, appearance, function, and conformance to the description, will provide a positive experience for consumers. The more a product's quality matches expectations, the more likely consumers are to make a purchase decision.

Buying decision

A purchase decision is a consumer's final action to select and purchase a preferred brand or product, after going through an evaluation process and forming a purchase intention. However, this decision can still be influenced by two factors: the opinions of others and unforeseen situational factors (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018: 179). According to Annafik & Rahardjo (in Tri Nuryani et al., 2022:454) purchasing decisions are the way in which consumers make decisions between several brands, and finally buy the ones they like or the process discussed by consumers in determining the goods or services they will buy based on various considerations. According to Kotler et al., (2022: 154–157), the purchasing decision process consists of several stages. This explains how consumers go through a series of processes starting from recognizing needs to finally making a purchasing decision, namely :

- Recognition of needs,
- Information search
- Alternative evaluation
- Buying decision
- Post-purchase behavior

According to Kotler & Keller (2016: 195–198) purchasing decisions have the following dimensions:

- Product choice, Consumers can make a decision to buy a product or use their money for other purposes.
- Choice of distributor, Consumers must make a decision about which distributor to visit.
- Purchase time, Purchase decisions in choosing the purchase time vary.
- Purchase Amount, Consumers can make decisions about how much product to spend at any one time.
- Payment method, Consumers can make decisions about the payment method that will be used when making decisions to use products or services.

Figure 1. Research Model

Research Hypothesis

Based on the background of the problem above, the hypothesis in this study is as follows:

H1: Digital Marketing and Product Quality simultaneously have a significant influence on Purchasing Decisions at Times Florist, Palu City.

H2: Digital Marketing has a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions at Times Florist, Palu City.

H3: Product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions at Times Florist, Palu City.

METHOD

research uses a causal quantitative approach. According to Sugiyono, (2023:16-17) quantitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, collecting data using research instruments, statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. Population The research population was all Times Florist consumers. The sample size was determined using Roscoe's guidelines (in Sugiyono, 2020) which state that a feasible sample size is 10 times the number of variables . This study has 3 variables so the minimum sample requirement is $30 \times 3 = 90$ respondents . The sampling technique used

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purposive sampling , namely respondents who have purchased products at Times Florist. Data were collected using a Likert scale questionnaire (1–5) which was structured based on the dimensions of digital marketing, product quality, and purchasing decisions The instrument was tested using validity (Corrected Item–Total Correlation > 0.30) and reliability (Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.60) (Santoso, 2021:126,132). Items that met both criteria were deemed suitable for use Data analysis was carried out using classical assumption tests , including normality tests (data is normal if Sig > 0.05), multicollinearity tests using Tolerance values (> 0.10) and VIF (<10), and heteroscedasticity tests to ensure there are no specific patterns in the scatterplot graph (Ghozali in Aditiya et al., 2023) . This was followed by multiple linear regression analysis . Hypothesis testing was carried out using the F test , t test , and coefficient of determination (R²) to see the magnitude and direction of the influence between variables. To make things easier, researchers compile operational definitions intended to describe the variables that arise from a study into more detailed indicators.

Table 1. Operational definitions of variables

Variables	Dimensions	Indicator
Digital Marketing X1	Interactive	1. Ease of interaction
		2. Fast response from seller
	Incentive program	3. Interesting program
		4. Special offer
	Site design	5. Attractive appearance
		6. Clear product information
	Cost	7. Cost efficiency
		8. Time efficiency
Product Quality X2	Product Features	9. Uniqueness
		10. Variation
	Product Durability	11. Product durability
		12. Not easily damaged
	Product Reliability	13. Quality consistency
		14. Conformity of results
	Conformance to Specifications	15. As requested
		16. The right size
	Product Aesthetics	17. Beautiful Design
		18. Neatness
Purchase Decision Y	Product Selection	19. Product variety
		20. Suitability of needs
	Distributor Options	21. Strategic location
		22. recommendation
	Purchase Time	23. Availability
		24. Speed of service
	Purchase Amount	25. Unlimited
		26. Flexibility of quantity
Payment Methods	27. Convenience	
	28. Comfort	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

Table 2. Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency n	Percentage %
Gender	Woman	63	70%
Age	17-25 years	60	66.7%
Education	Students	59	65.6%
Income	Rp. 1,000,000 – Rp. 2,000,000	33	36.7%

Source: Data processed by researchers

Based on the results of data processing, the majority of respondents in this study were women (70%) , with an age range of 17–25 years (66.7%) , dominated by students (65.6%) . In addition, most respondents have a monthly income of IDR 1,000,000–IDR 2,000,000 (36.7%) . This finding indicates that Times Florist consumers mainly come from young people who actively use social media and often follow bouquet purchasing trends, so this group is the main target market for the business.

Data Instrument Test

According to Sugiyono (2023:156), a research instrument is a tool used to measure observed natural or social phenomena. Research instruments are used as data collection tools, and the instruments commonly used in research are lists of statements and questionnaires that are delivered and given to each respondent who is part of the research sample.

Validity Test Results

Table 3. Validity Test

Research Variables	Research Instruments	Correlation Coefficient	Information
Digital Marketing	X1.1	0.389	Valid
	X1.2	0.672	Valid
	X1.3	0.460	Valid
	X1.4	0.670	Valid
	X1.5	0.635	Valid
	X1.6	0.515	Valid
	X1.7	0.661	Valid
	X1.8	0.779	Valid
Product Quality	X2.1	0.717	Valid
	X2.2	0.489	Valid
	X2.3	0.398	Valid
	X2.4	0.579	Valid
	X2.5	0.489	Valid
	X2.6	0.517	Valid
	X2.7	0.493	Valid
	X2.8	0.757	Valid
	X2.9	0.489	Valid
	X2.10	0.711	Valid
Buying decision	Y.1	0.326	Valid
	Y.2	0.811	Valid
	Y.3	0.371	Valid
	Y.4	0.847	Valid
	Y.5	0.326	Valid
	Y.6	0.849	Valid
	Y.7	0.897	Valid
	Y.8	0.867	Valid
	Y.9	0.882	Valid
	Y.10	0.450	Valid

Source: Data processed by researchers (2025)

Validity testing is used to measure the validity of a questionnaire. Based on Table 3 above, it can be concluded that all instruments contained in each variable are valid and can be used to measure all observed variables, as the correlation coefficient value is greater than 0.3 ($r \geq 0.3$). Therefore, it can be concluded that all statement items are valid.

Reliability Test Results

Table 4. Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Information
Digital marketing X1	0.851	8	Reliable
Product Quality X2	0.855	10	Reliable
Purchase Decision Y	0.912	10	Reliable

Source : Data processed by researchers (2025)

According to Santoso (2021:132), reliability is the extent to which an instrument can produce consistent and reliable results. A measuring instrument is said to be reliable if it is used repeatedly on the same subject and produces relatively consistent scores, as long as the measured data remain unchanged. Based on Table 3 above, the Cronbach's Alpha value for each variable is greater than 0.60 (≥ 0.60), thus it can be concluded that all instruments in this study are reliable.

Classical Assumption Test

This study uses the classical assumption test to evaluate the multiple linear regression model used to produce ideal values.

Normality Test

Table 5. Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
N		90
Normal Parameters ^{ab}	Mean	0,0000000
	Std. Deviation	2,00188172
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,086
	Positive	0,083
	Negative	-0,086
Test Statistic		0,086
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.098 ^c

Source : Data processed by researchers (2025)

The normality test is used to assess whether the confounding variables or residuals in a regression model follow a normal distribution (Ghozali in Aditiya et al., 2023) . Based on Table 5 above, the Asymp. Sig (2 -tailed) result using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is 0.098. Therefore, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed, because the significance value is greater than 0.05.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 6. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics	
Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	Digital Marketing X1	0.247	4,054
	Product Quality X2	0.247	4,054

a. Dependent Variable: Y: Purchase Decision

Source : Data processed by researchers (2025)

The multicollinearity test aims to ensure that the regression model has a high or perfect correlation between the independent variables used (Ghozali in Aditiya et al., 2023). Based on the table above, each independent variable has a tolerance value > 0.1 and a VIF value < 10. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in this regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on the image above, in the scatterplot graph, it can be seen that the points are spread randomly and are spread both above and below the number zero on the Y axis. So it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in this regression model.

Hypothesis Testing

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-0.725	1,961		-0.370	0.713
	Digital Marketing X1	0.759	0.112	0.563	6,750	0.000
	Product Quality X2	0.417	0.089	0.391	4,686	0,000
R = 0.922					F = 248.190	
R-Square = 0.851					Sig.-F = 0.000	
Adjusted R Square = 0.847						

Source : Data processed by researchers (2025)

Based on Table 7, it is known that the constant is -0.725, the digital marketing coefficient is 0.759, and the product quality coefficient is 0.417, so the regression formulation is as follows:

$$Y = -0.725 + 0.759X_1 + 0.417X_2$$

It can be concluded that the results of the multiple linear regression test are as follows:

- A constant value of -0.725 indicates that without the contribution of digital marketing and product quality, the purchase decision level is at a lower baseline. This means that both variables are necessary for increased purchase decisions.
- The digital marketing coefficient is 0.759, indicating that increasing digital marketing activity will increase purchasing decisions. Conversely, decreasing digital marketing strategies will decrease purchasing decisions. This confirms that digital promotions play a significant role in influencing consumer purchasing decisions.
- The product quality coefficient is 0.417, indicating that higher product quality increases purchasing decisions. Decreased product quality leads to decreased purchasing decisions. Therefore, neatness, aesthetics, and durability remain key factors for consumers.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Based on Table 7 above, the analysis results show an R-square value of 0.851, indicating that digital marketing and product quality can explain 85.1% of the variation in purchasing decisions. The adjusted R-square value of 0.847 confirms that the regression model used is stable and has excellent predictive capabilities. Thus, only 14.9% of the variation in purchasing decisions is influenced by factors other than the research model.

F test

Based on Table 7 above, the analysis results show a significant F value of 0.000, which is lower than the standard significance value of 0.05. This means that digital marketing and product quality variables simultaneously have a significant influence on purchasing decisions at Times Florist in Palu City. Therefore, it can be concluded that H1 is accepted.

T-test

Based on table 7 above, the t-value of Digital Marketing (X1) is 6.750 at sig $0.000 \leq 0.05$, meaning that Digital Marketing has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. So it can be concluded that H2 is accepted. Meanwhile, product quality (X2) with a t-value of 4.686 at sig $0.001 \leq 0.05$ means that product quality has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. So it can be concluded that H3 is accepted. From both calculations, it is found that Digital Marketing and product quality partially influence purchasing decisions.

Discussion

The Influence of Digital Marketing and Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions

Simultaneously, both variables produced an R Square value of 0.851, meaning digital marketing and product quality were able to explain 85.1% of the variation in purchasing decisions. This high figure confirms that these two factors are important determinants of Times Florist consumer behavior. The F-test significance value (0.000) also confirms that the overall regression model is suitable for use.

The Influence of Digital Marketing on Purchasing Decisions

Digital marketing has been shown to have the greatest influence with a regression coefficient of 0.759, indicating that the better the digital marketing strategy used, the higher the consumer's tendency to make a purchase. This is understandable because the majority of respondents are women aged 17–25, who are active social media users. Attractive visual content, fast seller response, and complete product information have been proven effective in shaping interest and ultimately driving purchasing decisions. This finding supports research by Sesandi et al., (2024), Soemadi, (2023), and Fanlikhin et al., (2023), which all state that digital marketing has a positive influence on purchasing decisions.

The Influence of Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions

Product quality also has a significant influence with a regression coefficient of 0.417. This means that aspects such as neatness of design, product durability, suitability to customer demand, and aesthetic appearance play an important role in driving purchasing decisions. This is consistent with Times Florist's condition in an area of intense competition, so product quality is a differentiating factor from other bouquet shops. This finding supports research by Ratnasari & Ali (2025) which states that product quality plays a central role in creating satisfaction and purchasing decisions. These results demonstrate that a consistent digital marketing strategy and improved product quality are key priorities for Times Florist. Aesthetically pleasing visual content, responsive interactions, and neat, well-presented bouquets that meet expectations can boost consumer trust and encourage purchase.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that digital marketing and product quality have a significant influence on purchasing decisions at Times Florist in Palu City. The digital marketing strategy implemented, particularly through social media, is able to increase product visibility and attract consumer interest. Meanwhile, good product quality, including neatness, beautiful design, and product durability, are important factors that strengthen consumer confidence in making purchasing decisions. Simultaneously, these two variables make a real contribution to encouraging increased purchasing decisions. Thus, increasing the effectiveness of digital marketing and maintaining consistent product quality are aspects that Times Florist needs to continue to pay attention to to maintain competitiveness and meet consumer needs.

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